

Mapping Large Memory-constrained Workflows onto Heterogeneous Platforms

Abstract—Scientific workflows are often represented as directed acyclic graphs (DAGs), where vertices correspond to tasks and edges represent the dependencies between them. Since these graphs are often large in both the number of tasks and their resource requirements, it is important to schedule them efficiently on parallel or distributed compute systems. Typically, each task requires a certain amount of memory to be executed and needs to communicate data to its successor tasks. The goal is thus to execute the workflow as fast as possible (i.e., to minimize its makespan) while satisfying the memory constraints and using parallelism to speed up the execution.

Hence, we investigate the partitioning and mapping of DAG-shaped workflows onto heterogeneous platforms where each processor can have a different memory size and a different processor speed. We first propose a baseline algorithm in the absence of existing solutions. As our main contribution, we then present a four-step heuristic. Its first step is to partition the input DAG into smaller blocks with an existing DAG partitioning algorithm. The next two steps adapt the blocks of the DAG to fit the processor memories and optimize for the overall makespan by further splitting and merging workflow blocks. Finally, we use local search (swapping of blocks) to achieve further improvements in makespan. Our experimental evaluation on real-world and simulated workflows shows that exploiting the heterogeneity in the cluster with the four-step heuristic reduces the makespan by a factor of 2.44 on average, compared to the baseline approach that only takes memory sizes into account.

Index Terms—Workflow mapping, DAG partitioning and scheduling, memory constraints, heterogeneous platforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many large scientific applications, *e. g.*, for data analysis, are nowadays often comprised of different software components expressed as tasks within a workflow [1]. Examples for such tasks can be data acquisition, data cleansing, various data analysis tasks, and visualization of the results [2] – executed on each data set. Such workflows are typically represented as directed acyclic graphs (DAGs); the vertices in the DAG represent the task and the edges express (input/output) dependencies between them [3], [4]. Such workflows can be very large as well as memory- and compute-intensive, so that they exhaust the resources of a single machine and need to be executed on a parallel or distributed system.

For an efficient execution, the workflow should be mapped to the system appropriately; one must decide which task is executed on which processor. This requires to partition the workflow into smaller sub-DAGs and to assign each sub-DAG to one processor. When doing so, a common objective function to minimize is the makespan, *i. e.*, the total running time of the workflow [5]. Since parallel and distributed systems such as (networks of) compute clusters are often heterogeneous in

terms of memory size and/or processor speed, these different properties of the individual compute nodes should be taken into account for a high-quality mapping. In particular, the memory size of a compute node should not be exceeded by a task, because otherwise the execution will fail. This leads to the following optimization problem: given a workflow in form of a weighted DAG $G = (V, E)$ and a compute system \mathcal{C} with k processors, compute an acyclic k -way partition of G such that the makespan is minimized. This is an \mathcal{NP} -hard problem [6], so that large workflows are handled by heuristics in practice. While there certainly are heterogeneity-aware (*e. g.*, [7]) and memory-aware (*e. g.*, [8]) techniques, we do not know of algorithms nor tools that simultaneously handle large DAGs, minimize the makespan, and respect memory constraints on the tasks.

Contributions: In this paper, we investigate the memory-constrained partitioning and mapping of DAG-shaped workflows onto heterogeneous platforms, where each processor can have a different memory size and a different processor speed. To this end, in the absence of heterogeneity-aware tools that also adhere to the memory constraints, we first propose a baseline algorithm that produces valid solutions, building on a memory-efficient traversal of the DAG. As our main contribution, we then present a partitioning-based heuristic with four steps: (i) partition the input DAG into smaller blocks with an existing DAG partitioning algorithm, (ii) adapt the blocks of the DAG to fit the processor memories, (iii) optimize for the overall makespan by further splitting and merging workflow blocks, and (iv) local search (swapping of blocks) to further improve the makespan. Our extensive experimental evaluation on real-world and simulated workflows shows that exploiting the heterogeneity in the cluster with the four-step heuristic reduces the makespan by a factor 2.44 on average compared to the baseline approach that only takes memory sizes into account. The gain goes up to being 5 times faster with big workflows and a large cluster configuration.

Outline: We survey the related work in Section II. Section III presents the model and formally introduces the optimization problem tackled in this paper. Heuristics are described in Section IV, and both the experimental setting and detailed results are presented in Section V. Finally, we conclude and provide directions for future work in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

The problem of executing a collection of tasks on various types of computing platforms has received long-standing re-

search attention [5]. With the increasing number of scientific workflows that need to be executed multiple times, this problem has gained renewed interest. Currently, the most common way of representing a workflow consists in modeling it as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) [3], [4], hence having the most general representation of dependence constraints.

Large-scale workflows are to be executed on parallel or distributed platforms, and the mapping problem consists in deciding where to execute each part of the workflow, guided by a target objective function. Usually, the goal is to execute the entire workflow as fast as possible, hence to minimize the *makespan*, or total execution time [5], [9], [10].

However, while performance is the objective, one must at the same time account for the constraints given by the execution platform. In particular, since memory and I/O become a bottleneck [11], [12], one must make sure that each processor has a local memory large enough to execute the part of the workflow that has been mapped on it. For shared-memory platforms (we assume distributed memory instead), Bathie *et al.* [8] propose, among others, a dynamic memory-aware DAG scheduling heuristic based on an ILP formulation. Their optimization objective is cut-based and the overall approach is limited to rather small workflows.

Scheduling for heterogeneous platforms has been investigated in the past already [7], [13], of course. In particular, it has been remarked that the consideration of heterogeneity is a crucial aspect in scheduling algorithms for cloud platforms [14]. For scheduling tree-shaped workflows (a special case of the DAGs considered here), Kulagina *et al.* [15] showed that taking different memory sizes and processor speeds into account can improve the makespan considerably. More precisely, they extend a partitioning-based heuristic that maps trees on homogeneous platforms [16] to make it heterogeneity-aware. A similar goal is pursued by He *et al.* [17] with their tree mapping algorithm.

When moving from tree-shaped workflows to the case of general DAGs, the relatively simple partitioning approaches above do not work any longer. That is why we employ DAG partitioning, for which several tools exist, among them DAGP [18]. Techniques for partitioning general undirected graphs are numerous [19], but in many cases not easily transferable to the DAG case. Note that partitioning into (nearly-)balanced (and in case of DAGs, acyclic) blocks is \mathcal{NP} -hard both for general graphs [6] and for DAGs [20].

We are not the first to employ DAG partitioning for scheduling. The problem of memory minimization for series-parallel DAGs has been tackled by [21]. The authors propose an algorithm that fits parts of the workflow into memories of adequate size, but they do not aim at makespan optimization. Also, Özkaya *et al.* [22] build a scheduler based on their partitioner DAGP. This scheduler uses the DAGP output and then uses a list-based scheduling approach to optimize for makespan. However, this scheduler does not take memory constraints into account, and it is therefore not applicable for our target problem.

III. MODEL

We first describe the target applications, which are (large scientific) workflows, in Section III-A. Next, we define the execution environment, a heterogeneous cluster, in Section III-B. We provide details about the optimization objective, which is to minimize the makespan, in Section III-C. Finally, we are ready to express the optimization problem in Section III-D.

Table I summarizes the main notation.

A. Workflow

A workflow is a directed acyclic graph $G = (V, E)$, where V is the set of vertices (tasks), and E is a set of directed edges of the form $e = (u, v)$, with $u, v \in V$, expressing precedence constraints between tasks. Each task $u \in V$ is performing w_u operations, and it also requires some memory to be executed, denoted as m_u . Each edge $e = (u, v)$ has a cost $c_{u,v}$ that corresponds to the size of the output file written by task u and used as input by task v .

Hence, the total memory requirement of task u consists of the input files (size of the files to be received from the parents), the output files (size of the files to be sent to the children), and the memory size m_u . In total, a task u requires the following amount of memory for its execution:

$$r_u = \sum_{v:(v,u) \in E} c_{v,u} + m_u + \sum_{v:(u,v) \in E} c_{u,v}.$$

The maximum memory requirement of the workflow, r_{\max} , is $\max_{u \in V} r_u$.

The parents of a task $u \in V$ are the tasks that should be executed and complete before u , i.e., the set of parents is $\Pi_u = \{v \in V : (v, u) \in E\}$. A task without parents is called a *source task*. The children tasks of u are the tasks following u according to the precedence constraints, i.e., $C_u = \{v \in V : (u, v) \in E\}$. A task without children is called a *target task*. Note that since the workflow is an arbitrary DAG, each task may have multiple parents and children.

Symbol	Meaning
$G = (V, E)$	Workflow graph, set of vertices (tasks) and edges
Π_u, C_u	Parents of a task u , children of a task u
m_u	Memory weight of task u
w_u	Workload of task u (normalized execution time)
$c_{u,v}$	Communication volume along the edge $(u, v) \in E$
F, \mathcal{F}	A partitioning function and the partition it creates
V_i	Block number i
\mathcal{C}, k	Compute system and the number of processors in it
$p_j, \text{proc}(V_i)$	Processor number j , processor of block V_i
M_j, s_j	Memory size and speed of processor p_j
β	Bandwidth in the compute system
l_u	Bottom weight of task u
μ_G, μ_i	Makespan of the entire workflow G and of a block V_i
$\Gamma = (V, \mathcal{E})$	Quotient graph, its vertices and its edges
r_u, r_{V_i}	Memory requirement of task u and of block V_i
r_{\max}	Maximum memory requirement in a workflow
\mathcal{P}	Critical path in a workflow

TABLE I
NOTATION

B. Execution environment

The goal is to execute the workflow on a heterogeneous cluster \mathcal{C} that consists of k processors p_1, \dots, p_k . Each processor p_j ($1 \leq j \leq k$) has an individual memory size M_j and a speed s_j . The execution time of a single task $u \in V$ on a processor p_j is expressed as $\frac{w_u}{s_j}$. We assume that all processors are connected with the same bandwidth β .

In general, more than just one task can be mapped on the same processor; hence we aim at partitioning the tasks into blocks, where each block will be mapped on a distinct processor. A *partitioning function* is a function $F : V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ that assigns each task a number, corresponding to its block number. The i -th block, denoted as V_i , contains all tasks that have been assigned number i : $V_i = \{u \in V : F(u) = i\}$. \mathcal{F} is the partition, *i. e.*, the set of blocks that F creates.

If block $V_i \in \mathcal{F}$ has been assigned to a processor $p_j \in \mathcal{C}$, we say that $p_j = \text{proc}(V_i)$. Furthermore, the maximum memory requirement of a block V_i is r_{V_i} , and it depends on the order in which the block, which is a DAG, is executed. We use the MEMDAG algorithm from [21] to compute this memory requirement r_{V_i} , by transforming block V_i into a series-parallel graph, and then finding the traversal that leads to the minimum memory consumption.

C. Makespan computation

Before expressing the makespan of a workflow G , given a mapping on a cluster \mathcal{C} , we start with a few definitions.

The *bottom weight* l_u of a task $u \in V$ is defined as:

$$l_u = \begin{cases} \frac{w_u}{s_u} & \text{if } C_u = \emptyset, \\ \frac{w_u}{s_u} + \max_{v \in C_u} \left\{ \frac{c_{u,v}}{\beta} + l_v \right\} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where s_u is the speed of the processor that task u has been assigned to. If task u has not been assigned to any processor, then the speed is assumed to be 1.

A quotient DAG $\Gamma = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ is built from a DAG G and a partitioning function F as defined in Section III-B, assuming that the partition does not create cycles (and hence Γ is a DAG). Each quotient DAG vertex $\nu_i \in \mathcal{V}$ corresponds to a block V_i of the *original* DAG G . The weights on ν_i are defined as $w_{\nu_i} = \sum_{u \in V_i} w_u$, while edge weights $c_{\nu_i, \nu_j} = \sum_{u \in V_i, v \in V_j} c_{u,v}$ are the sum of weights of all the edges between the two corresponding blocks. We define the *makespan* of a graph G via the corresponding quotient graph Γ . The makespan of Γ equals the maximum of the bottom weights of the tasks in it: $\mu(\Gamma) = \max_{\nu \in \mathcal{V}} l_\nu$. In case of a single source, this maximum is achieved on the source task.

In Γ , each block can be assigned to a different processor, so the makespan weights and the critical path change when the assignment to processors change.

An unpartitioned DAG G corresponds to a quotient DAG Γ with only one task ν_1 , and it is always executed on a single processor, s_j . Therefore, its makespan is the sum of makespan weights of its nodes divided by this processor's speed: $\mu_G =$

$\sum_{v \in V} \frac{w_v}{s_j}$. Because no files need to be transferred, edge weights play no role.

The makespan is entirely defined once we have a mapping of the workflow onto the target cluster \mathcal{C} , and hence we can account for processor speeds. If the mapping is not complete yet, as mentioned in the bottom weights definition, a speed of 1 is assumed, so that the bottom weights can still be computed with this assumption, leading to an *estimated makespan*. If parts of the workflow have already been assigned, the corresponding speed is used for these tasks.

Finally, note that in the definition, the finishing time of block V_i is equal to the finishing time of all the tasks within this block, since we sum up all task weights before doing the communications and moving up to the next block. In reality, some tasks may finish before the block finishes, and their successors could start earlier, but we do not consider this possibility, hence providing in fact an overestimation of the makespan.

D. Problem formulation

We formulate the DAGP-PM problem (**DAG Partitioning with Proportionate blocks and minimized Makespan**).

DAGP-PM problem. Let $\mathcal{C} = p_1, \dots, p_k$ be the execution environment consisting of k processors. Each processor p_j (for $1 \leq j \leq k$) has an individual memory size M_j . Given a DAG $G = (V, E)$, find an acyclic k -way partitioning function F , its corresponding partition $\{V_1, \dots, V_k\}$ of V , and a mapping of blocks V_i to processors such that

$$\text{proc}(V_i) \neq \text{proc}(V_j), \quad 1 \leq i \neq j \leq k$$

$$r_{V_i} \leq M_i, \quad \text{where } p_i = \text{proc}(V_i)$$

and the induced makespan is minimized.

Note that this DAGP-PM problem is (when formulated as decision problem) obviously NP-complete, even without memory constraints and precedence constraints. Indeed, the problem of scheduling independent tasks with different execution times, even on a homogeneous platform, is well-known to be NP-complete (trivial equivalence to 2-partition or 3-partition [9]). We are facing a complex problem, and the core contribution is to design a heuristic solution method, DAGHETPART, which accounts for the heterogeneity of the target platform while respecting the memory constraints.

IV. HEURISTICS

Before describing the DAGHETPART heuristic that accounts for the platform heterogeneity, we start with a baseline heuristic, building on related work, that aims at returning a valid mapping of the DAG. The goal is to focus on the memory constraints, since no existing (makespan-oriented) mapping algorithm, to the best of our knowledge, is addressing these constraints and is able to return a valid solution to the DAGP-PM problem.

Section IV-A presents this baseline heuristic DAGHETMEM, and then Section IV-B details how DAGHETPART is working.

A. Baseline memory-aware heuristic – DAGHETMEM

The DAGHETMEM heuristic is directly building upon the MEMDAG algorithm [21]. MEMDAG computes an optimal traversal of the workflow graph G that minimizes the peak memory consumption. Also, the processors are sorted by decreasing memory sizes. Hence, if the peak memory is lower than the largest memory available, the whole DAG can be mapped on a single processor and a valid mapping is found.

However, this baseline is not always feasible for large workflows. If this is the case, we perform the traversal returned by MEMDAG, and add tasks in the first part (block V_1) as long as the memory requirement of the current (largest) processor is not exceeded. The update to the memory requirement is done each time a new task is traversed, by adding its memory requirement, subtracting the memory requirement of the task executed beforehand, and updating edge weights that should remain in memory.

If the traversal of a given task $u \in V$ leads to a block whose memory requirement is exceeding the memory of the processor, we remove u from the block. We start creating the next block on the next available processor, starting again from a memory of zero, and resuming the traversal from task u that initiates the new block.

Hence, the heuristic proceeds iteratively, following the order of the initial traversal returned by MEMDAG, and creating a new part as necessary. It ends successfully when all tasks have been traversed, or it may fail if there are some remaining tasks but no more processors available.

Once the blocks have been generated, the quotient graph can be computed, based on the part numbers. Note that parts are not necessarily connected graphs, since we follow the traversal order. But given the quotient graph, it is possible to compute the makespan achieved by this mapping, as explained in Section III-C. Note that this baseline algorithm is not trying to optimize the makespan, but it produces a valid solution that respects the memory constraints if it is successful. However, it does not exploit the parallelism in the DAG, in particular not for workflows that fit on a single processor memory-wise.

Hence, we focus in the following on the design of a heuristic for the DAGP-PM problem, aiming at minimizing the makespan while respecting memory constraints.

B. Partitioning-based heuristic – DAGHETPART

The DAGHETPART heuristic is going beyond DAGHETMEM and aims at minimizing the makespan. Since there are many constraints, the key idea is to decompose the heuristic into several steps; each step builds upon the previous one to improve the solution and adapt it to the platform.

In the first step, we use an existing DAG partitioning algorithm to obtain the initial blocks that will be used by our heuristic (hence its name DAGHETPART). This step ignores all the heterogeneity (memory size, processor speed) in the execution environment and optimizes for the smallest edge cut. In the second step, we create a preliminary assignment of these first blocks to processors, changing their size if necessary to fit them into the memories of given processors. This step respects

the memory heterogeneity, but ignores the different processor speeds. The third step incorporates the processor speeds to optimize the makespan, and it merges blocks if there are more blocks than processors, until it obtains a valid assignment of blocks to processors (or failure). Finally, the fourth step starts with a valid assignment and tries to improve it by local search. Two blocks are swapped (from one processor to another) if the operation is possible memory-wise and if it brings the biggest improvement in makespan among all other possible swaps. If there are free processors, we also try to move blocks to one of these processors if it improves the makespan.

We now detail each of the four steps.

Step 1: Partitioning

We use the edge-cut-optimizing acyclic graph partitioner DAGP [18] for the first step. This partitioner takes a DAG as input, which is the workflow G that we aim at mapping on the cluster \mathcal{C} . We also specify the number of parts, *i. e.*, in how many blocks we want to partition G . Since the target platform has k processors, we create an initial partition into k blocks with DAGP. This step returns the initial partitioning function in the form of an array of block numbers. For instance, with $n = 5$ tasks and $k = 2$ processors, we may obtain a result $[1,1,1,2,2]$ meaning that tasks 1,2 and 3 are in the same block V_1 , and tasks 4 and 5 are in another block V_2 .

Step 2: Assignment

We start with the partitioning function obtained from Step 1, and we insert the resulting blocks into a priority queue Q – with the required block memory size as priority. The processors, in turn, are inserted into a queue M in descending order w.r.t. their available memory size (see Algorithm 1). Then, we assign the largest block to the free processor with the largest memory as long as there are remaining blocks and processors (while loop starting in Line 7). During this assignment (algorithm FITBLOCK), it may happen that the block does not fit on the processor, *i. e.*, its memory requirement exceeds the memory available on the processor. In this case the block is further partitioned, and the resulting sub-blocks are inserted back into the queue Q . Hence, the size of Q can become bigger than that of M . If this happens, the unassigned blocks are further partitioned (loop of Line 15) to the size of the memory of the smallest processor in the cluster – by another call to FITBLOCK that will not perform any assignment.

Algorithm 2 describes the fitting procedure in details. Its input is the block V_i to be fitted, the priority queue of blocks, the processor where the block should be scheduled on, and a flag `doMap` which indicates that we really want to place the block on this processor – rather than just partitioning it down to the processor’s memory size. If a block V_i fits on the desired processor and if the flag is true, the block is mapped on its target processor (Line 4) and the algorithm returns the block that was placed. Otherwise, we further partition this block using the same partitioner as in Step 1 (Line 8 in Algorithm 2). Although we strive for dividing the block into two new blocks, sometimes DAGP cannot do that due to

Algorithm 1 BIGGESTASSIGN

```
1: procedure BIGGESTASSIGN( $\mathcal{F}$ ,  $\mathcal{C}$ )
2:    $\triangleright$  Input: initial partition  $\mathcal{F}$ , cluster  $\mathcal{C}$ 
3:   Init PQ  $Q$  with  $\mathcal{F}$ ;
4:    $\triangleright$  max-priority queue of the blocks
5:   Init queue  $M$  with  $\mathcal{C}$ ;
6:    $\triangleright$  a queue of processors sorted by memory size
7:   while not  $Q.empty()$  and not  $M.empty()$  do
8:      $V_m \leftarrow Q.extractMax()$ ;  $p_m \leftarrow M.head()$ ;
9:      $V_r \leftarrow \text{FITBLOCK}(V_m, Q, p_m, true)$ ;
10:     $\triangleright$  Fit the block while actually trying to map it
11:    if  $V_r \neq \text{NULL}$  then  $M.remove(p_m)$ ;
12:     $\triangleright$  Remove the processor that is now busy
13:  end if
14: end while
15: while not  $Q.empty()$  do  $\triangleright$  No more procs, but
    remaining partition blocks
16:    $V_m \leftarrow Q.extractMax()$ ;  $p_m \leftarrow \min M(\mathcal{C})$ ;
17:    $\triangleright$   $p_m$  is the proc. with the smallest memory
18:    $\text{FITBLOCK}(V_m, Q, p_m, false)$ ;
19:  $\triangleright$  Fit the block without actually putting it on the proc.
20: end while
21: end procedure
```

balancing constraints. Hence, PARTITION may generate more than two blocks. We then insert the resulting blocks back into the queue Q and a NULL result is returned, indicating that no block has been placed on the processor. Because Q is a priority queue, it maintains the correct ordering of blocks sorted by their memory requirement. Otherwise, a relatively small block obtained during repartitioning could block a relatively big waiting block from being assigned.

Step 2 returns at least a valid partial assignment of blocks to processors, but not yet necessarily a complete one: all assigned blocks have to fit, but some blocks may not be assigned yet.

Step 3: Merging

The focus of this step lies in the makespan, affected by heterogeneous processor speeds. We operate on the quotient graph Γ that is built from the original graph G using the blocks from Step 2 and their (partial) assignment to processors. According to the definition of the quotient graph, each block V_i of the original graph becomes a vertex in Γ . Since the assignment in Step 2 may have been incomplete, some of these vertices are assigned to processors, while some may not. We try to improve the makespan by merging unassigned vertices in Γ to the assigned ones in a way that impairs the makespan the least. Because there are still unassigned vertices, we operate with the *estimated makespan* for this step.

We first observe that merging two unassigned vertices in Γ will not help our cause: such a merge results in a bigger, still unassigned vertex that will be more difficult to place on a processor. Therefore, we merge an unassigned vertex with an assigned one.

Algorithm 2 FITBLOCK

```
1: procedure FITBLOCK( $V_i, Q, p_j, \text{doMap}$ )  $\triangleright$ 
   Input: a block  $V_i$  that needs to be fitted, priority queue
    $Q$  of other blocks, available proc.  $p_j$ , a flag  $\text{doMap}$  that
   indicates that we want to map the resulting subtree on the
   processor
2:   if  $r_{V_i} \leq M_j$  then
3:     if  $\text{doMap}$  then
4:        $\text{proc}(V_i) \leftarrow p_j$ ;
5:       return  $V_i$ ;
6:     end if
7:   else
8:      $(V_{i_1}, V_{i_2}, \dots) \leftarrow \text{PARTITION}(V_i, 2)$ ;
9:     for  $V_k \in \{V_{i_1}, V_{i_2}, \dots\}$  do
10:       $Q.add(V_k)$ ;  $\triangleright$  Reinsert resulting blocks
11:    end for
12:   end if
13:   return NULL;
14: end procedure
```

The next observation is that the makespan is constrained by the critical path in Γ . Indeed, the critical path is the one that dictates the makespan in the computation of the bottom weights (see Eq. (1)). Merging more vertices to one that lies on the critical path will increase the makespan, while merging outside of the critical path will only affect the makespan if the merge changes the critical path. Therefore, we prefer merging an unassigned vertex outside of the critical path to another vertex that is not on the critical path, but we still allow merges on the critical path if no other solution is possible. In particular, if a node on the critical path is not assigned and considered for merging, it might be interesting to merge it to its father or children, hence saving communication costs on the critical path.

First, let us consider an algorithm that finds the best possible merge for a single quotient vertex ν (Algorithm 3). It takes the vertex ν in question, a list of candidates that can be used for merging A , and the graph Γ as the input. We can merge ν to one of either its parents or its children, but only those that are in A (Line 4). For each such vertex ν' , we tentatively merge it with ν , an action that results in the creation of a new vertex ν_m , and changes Γ to Γ' (Line 5). In the bad case, Γ' contains cycles after this action, as in Fig. 1 if a and b are merged. In the general case, introducing a cycle into the graph is a reason to discard the tentative merge. However, there is one easily solvable case, illustrated by Fig. 1. In this case, the merge creates a cycle of length 2. This situation can (often) be resolved by merging the third vertex into the set.

This is exactly what we do if we encounter a cycle of length 2 (Line 7): we merge the already merged vertex ν_m with the second vertex in the cycle (Line 8). If the graph still has cycles after that, then we discard this merge: we unmerge ν_m and continue with another merge candidate for ν . Otherwise, we store the third vertex as ν_o , an optional third vertex, and operate on the graph Γ'' that contains this triple-merged vertex.

Fig. 1. Merging two vertices in an acyclic graph can create a cycle of length 2. Merging all three vertices may solve the problem.

Algorithm 3 FINDMSOPTMERGE

```

1: procedure MERGE( $\nu, A, \Gamma$ )  $\triangleright$  A block  $\nu$ 
   (vertex in  $\Gamma$ ) that needs to be merged, a set  $A$  of vertices
   that can be used for the merge, the graph  $\Gamma$ .
2:    $\mu_{min} \leftarrow +\infty; \nu_{min} \leftarrow NULL; \nu_o \leftarrow NULL;$ 
3:    $\triangleright \nu_o$  is an optional third vertex in the merge
4:   for  $\{\nu' \in \Pi_\nu \cup C_\nu\} \cap A$  do
5:      $\{\nu_m, \Gamma'\} \leftarrow \text{MERGE}(\nu, \nu');$ 
6:     if isCyclic( $\Gamma'$ ) then
7:       if Cycle( $\Gamma'$ ).size=2 then
8:          $\{\nu_m, \Gamma''\} \leftarrow \text{MERGE}(\nu_m, \text{Cycle}(\Gamma')[1]);$ 
9:         if isCyclic( $\Gamma''$ ) then
10:          UNMERGE( $\nu_m$ ); break;
11:        else
12:           $\nu_o \leftarrow \text{Cycle}(\Gamma)[1]; \Gamma' \leftarrow \Gamma'';$ 
13:        end if
14:      else
15:        UNMERGE( $\nu_m$ ); break;
16:      end if
17:    end if
18:    if  $r_{\nu_m} \leq M_{proc}(\nu')$  then
19:       $\mu \leftarrow \text{MAKESPAN}(\Gamma')$   $\triangleright$  Assess the impact of
   this merge on the makespan of the entire graph
20:      if  $\mu \leq \mu_{min}$  then
21:         $\mu_{min} \leftarrow \mu; \nu_{min} \leftarrow \nu';$ 
22:         $\Gamma \leftarrow \Gamma';$ 
23:      end if
24:    end if
25:    UNMERGE( $\nu_m$ );
26:  end for
27:  return  $(\mu_{min}, \nu_{min}, \nu_o);$ 
28: end procedure

```

If Γ' remains cycle-free or if a single 2-vertex cycle has been eliminated, we assess the quality of this merge (Line 18). The memory requirement of ν_m must not exceed the memory available on the processor of ν' , the merge candidate. We compute the makespan of the modified Γ' (Line 19). If this is the best makespan we have encountered yet, we store it and the vertex that allowed it (Line 20) and proceed to try out the next merge. We return the best makespan found, the vertex that yielded it, and the optional third vertex.

With Algorithm 3 described, we can now formulate the merging algorithm used in Step 3 (Algorithm 4). We first construct a quotient DAG Γ (Line 2) and compute its critical path \mathcal{P} . Each vertex in Γ additionally has a counter z (number

Algorithm 4 MERGEUNASSIGNEDTOASSIGNED

```

1: procedure STEP 3( $\{V_1 \dots V_k\}, P$ )  $\triangleright$  Input: Blocks
    $V_1 \dots V_k$ , processors  $P$ 
2:    $\Gamma \leftarrow \text{QUOTIENTDAG}(G, \{V_1 \dots V_k\})$   $\triangleright$  We build a
   quotient DAG from the block of  $G$ 
3:    $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \text{CRITICALPATH}(\Gamma)$ 
4:    $A \leftarrow \{\nu \in \mathcal{V} : \text{proc}(\nu) \neq NULL\}$   $\triangleright$  All assigned
   vertices
5:    $U \leftarrow \{\nu \in V(\Gamma) : \text{proc}(\nu) = NULL\}$   $\triangleright$  All
   unassigned vertices
6:   for  $\nu \in U$  do
7:      $U \leftarrow U \setminus \nu; \mu_{min} \leftarrow \infty; \nu_{min} \leftarrow NULL$ 
8:      $\mu_{min}, \nu_{min}, \nu_o \leftarrow \text{FINDMSOPTMERGE}(\nu, A \setminus$ 
    $\mathcal{P}, \Gamma)$ 
9:     if  $\nu_{min} \neq NULL$  then  $\triangleright$  Found a feasible merge
10:       $\{\nu_m, \Gamma'\} \leftarrow \text{MERGE}(\nu, \nu_{min}, \nu_o);$ 
11:       $\Gamma \leftarrow \Gamma'; A.\text{remove}(\nu_{min}); A.\text{remove}(\nu_o);$ 
12:       $\text{proc}(\nu_m) = \text{proc}(\nu_{min});$ 
13:       $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \text{CRITICALPATH}(\Gamma)$   $\triangleright$  Critical path could
   have changed after the merge.
14:     else  $\triangleright$  No feasible merge in  $A \setminus \mathcal{P}$ 
15:        $\mu_{min}, \nu_{min}, \nu_o \leftarrow \text{FINDMSOPT-$ 
    $\text{MERGE}(\nu, A, \Gamma)$   $\triangleright$  Look for a feasible merge anywhere in
    $\Gamma$ 
16:       if  $\nu_{min} \neq NULL$  then  $\triangleright$  Found a feasible
   merge somewhere
17:          $\{\nu_m, \Gamma'\} \leftarrow \text{MERGE}(\nu, \nu_{min}, \nu_o);$ 
18:          $\Gamma \leftarrow \Gamma'; A.\text{remove}(\nu_{min}); A.\text{remove}(\nu_o);$ 
19:          $\text{proc}(\nu_m) = \text{proc}(\nu_{min});$ 
20:          $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \text{CRITICALPATH}(\Gamma);$ 
21:       else
22:         if  $(C_\nu \cap U \neq \emptyset \text{ or } \Pi_\nu \cap U \neq \emptyset)$  and
    $\nu.c \leq 1$  then  $\triangleright$  Has unassigned parents or children
23:            $U \leftarrow U \cup \nu; \nu.c ++;$ 
24:         end if
25:       end if
26:       return false;
27:    $\triangleright$  We could not find a fit for a block, therefore we fail.
28:   end if
29: end for
30: return  $\Gamma;$ 
31: end procedure

```

of times it was seen) that is set to 0 at the beginning. Then, we build the set A of all assigned tasks (Line 4).

We iterate over all unassigned blocks (Line 6). When doing so, we first try to merge the unassigned block to an assigned one that is not on the critical path (Line 8). If a feasible merge has been found this way, we execute it in Line 10, then assign the resulting vertex to the processor, and recompute the critical path. Otherwise, we repeat the same attempt, but now we try to merge to any assigned task – no matter if it is on the critical path or not (Line 15). If this merge succeeds, we execute it in the same fashion. If no merge could have been found

even on the critical path, then we consider the possibility of trying to merge this vertex at a later point in time. If a vertex has unassigned parents or children, it may become mergeable later, when these parents or children have themselves been assigned (Line 22). In this case, we reinsert the vertex into the set of unassigned vertices to be checked later. However, to avoid a situation where two vertices are being constantly reinserted after each other, we use the counter $\nu.c$. We increase it on each reinsert and stop reinserting after 2 times.

Finally, we return the quotient graph (with the assigned tasks) if we succeed.

Step 4: Swaps

In Algorithm 5, we swap blocks using swap-based local search in order to further improve the makespan. We first identify all feasible swaps (pairs of vertices that fit into the respective memories of the processors of the other vertex) in Lines 5-6. The best swap is stored (Line 10) and executed. We stop when no more makespan-improving swaps can be made.

Furthermore, it may happen, in particular with small workflows, that the partitioner does not create enough blocks and some of the processors remain idle. In that case, some of these idle processors may be faster than those the blocks were assigned to. For this reason, we add one final step that is only activated if there are idle processors after swapping. In it, we go through the critical path of Γ and try to move each task to a faster idle processor that can hold it memory-wise. If such a processor exists, we move the task there and recompute the

critical path. We do this as long as there are tasks in the critical path that have not been moved.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Section V-A describes the setup for evaluating the DAGHET-PART heuristic, Section V-B presents the results.

A. Setup

All algorithms are implemented in C++ and compiled with g++ (v.11.2.0). The experiments are executed on workstations with 192 GB RAM and 2x 12-Core Intel Xeon 6126 @3.2 GHz and CentOS 8 as OS. The code and input data can be downloaded at <https://zenodo.org/record/8413672>.

We first describe the set of workflows used in the evaluation and then the clusters on which the workflows are to be mapped.

1) *Workflow instances*: The input data for the experiments consists of two sets of workflows: real-world workflows obtained from the <https://nf-co.re/> repository, and workflows obtained by simulating real-world workflows with the WFGGen generator (<https://wfcommons.org/generator>). First, we discuss how the graphs (*i.e.*, vertices and edges) are generated, and then we focus on the weights associated to tasks and edges.

a) *Workflow graphs*: For real-world workflows, their nextflow definition (see <https://github.com/nextflow-io/>) was downloaded from the respective repository and transformed into .dot format using the nextflow option “-with-dag”. The respective DAG contains many pseudo-tasks that do not correspond to actual tasks, but are only internal representations in nextflow. That is why we removed these internal tasks.

For the simulated workflows, the graph is produced by the WFGGen generator, based on a *model workflow* and the desired number of tasks. The model workflows are described on the WFGGen website, and we used the following ones: 1000Genome, BLAST, BWA, Epigenomics, Montage, Seismology, and SoyKB. Other models could not be generated without errors. As number of tasks, we use: 200, 1 000, 2 000, 4 000, 8 000, 10 000, 15 000, 18 000, 20 000, 25 000, 30 000. We divide the workflows into three groups by size: small ones with up to 8 000 tasks, middle ones with 10 000 to 18 000 tasks, and big ones with 20 000 to 30 000 tasks. Overall, this yields four workflow types: real-world, small, middle, and big.

b) *Generation of task and edge weights*: For the real-world workflows, we used historical data files provided by Bader *et al.* [23]. The columns in these files are measured Linux PS stats, acquired during an execution of a nextflow workflow. Each row corresponds to an execution of one task on one cluster node. Since the operating system cannot distinguish between the RAM the task uses for itself and the RAM it uses to store files that were sent or received from other tasks, the values in the historical data are total memory requirements (input/output files plus memory consumption of the computation). In a similar manner, the historical data provided by [23] does not store the actual weights of edges between tasks, but only the overall size of files that the task sends to all its children.

Algorithm 5 Swap PHASE A: SWAP THE BEST PAIR UNTIL NO FEASIBLE IMPROVING SWAP EXISTS

```

1: function SWAP( $\Gamma$ ,  $\mathcal{C}$ )  $\triangleright$  Quotient DAG  $\Gamma$  whose tasks  $\mathcal{V}$ 
   have been assigned to processors, cluster  $\mathcal{C}$ 
2:    $best \leftarrow \text{pair}(\Gamma, \text{makespan}(\Gamma));$ 
3:   while true do
4:      $curr \leftarrow best;$ 
5:     for all pairs  $(\nu, \nu')$  of  $\mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$  do
6:       if  $\text{isSwapFeasible}(best.first, \nu, \nu')$  then
7:          $\Gamma' \leftarrow \text{swap}(best.first, (\nu, \nu'));$ 
8:          $next \leftarrow \text{pair}(\Gamma', \text{MAKESPAN}(\Gamma'));$ 
9:         if  $next.second < curr.second$  then
10:           $curr \leftarrow next;$ 
11:           $\triangleright$  better solution is stored
12:        end if
13:      end if
14:    end for
15:    if  $curr.second < best.second$  then
16:       $best \leftarrow curr; \Gamma \leftarrow best.first;$ 
17:       $\triangleright$  execute improving swap and work further with the
      resulting quotient graph
18:    else return  $best;$ 
19:     $\triangleright$  stop because no improving swap exists
20:  end if
21: end while
22: end function

```

Processor name	CPU speed	Memory size
local	4	16
A1	32	32
A2	6	64
N1	12	16
N2	8	8
C2	32	192

TABLE II
CLUSTER CONFIGURATION (DEFAULT)

For each task, historical data can contain multiple values, obtained from the runs with different input sizes. To avoid underestimation, we take the maximum among all values from different runs on the same cluster node. Not all tasks have historical runtime data stored in the tables. In fact, for two workflows, Bader *et al.* do not provide data for more than 50% of the tasks. For two more, around 40% of tasks have no historical runtime data stored. Hence, in the absence of historical data about a task, we give it a weight of 1. Because the historical data contains absolute measured values and the cluster node information is a relative value, we normalize all values extracted from the historical data by the smallest one. This way, task memory weights fit into the memory of the cluster nodes. Additionally, this way, the tasks without historical data receive less insignificant values compared to tasks with historical data.

For the simulated workflows, we generate random execution times and memory weights for each task as well as edge weights for each precedence constraint. We generate uniformly distributed values between 1 and 10 for edge weights, 1 and 1000 for the workloads, and 1 and 192 for memory weights. When doing so, we try to mimic the weights observed in the historical data, hence *e.g.* the low lower bounds for the workloads.

2) *Target platform*: To fully benefit from the historical data, the *default* experimental environment that we consider is a cluster based on the same six kinds of nodes that are described and used in [23]. We set the amount of each kind of node to six, thus making it 36 processors in the cluster.

Table II contains the memory sizes and CPU speeds of these nodes. Note that, by its nature, this cluster setup corresponds to a cluster with some *luxury* nodes (C2), and some *weak* nodes (local, N2). Memory sizes are normalized values, relative to each other. Therefore, we additionally normalize memory weights of real-world workflows to the maximum size of 192 to make sure they fit. For simulated workflows, we increase memory sizes proportionally until the task with the biggest memory requirement has a processor it could be executed on.

In order to test various settings, we also vary the cluster configuration and consider variants of the default cluster presented above:

- *Small* and *large* clusters. While the default cluster consists of 36 nodes (6 of each kind), we consider a small cluster with three processors of each kind (18 processors in total), and a big cluster with ten processors of each

<i>MoreHet</i>	Speed	Memory	<i>LessHet</i>	Speed	Memory
local*	2	8	local'	8	64
A1*	64	64	A1'	16	64
A2*	3	128	A2'	12	128
N1*	24	8	N1'	12	64
N2*	4	4	N2'	16	32
C2*	64	384	C2'	16	192

TABLE III
CLUSTERS WITH MORE OR LESS HETEROGENEITY

kind (60 processors in total).

- More and less heterogeneous clusters (*MoreHet* and *LessHet*). In addition to the cluster in Table II, we also consider more and less heterogeneous clusters (Table III). For a cluster with more heterogeneity, the smaller half of memories have been made twice smaller, and the bigger half has been made twice bigger. The same holds for processor speeds. For the less heterogeneous cluster, a reverse procedure has been made: smaller values have been increased twice, while bigger values have been reduced. An exception has been made for the biggest memory size: we left it at 192 to make sure that the largest memory requirements of tasks could still be met.
- Finally, it is interesting to investigate the impact of the communication to computation ratio (*CCR*) by modifying the bandwidth β (also used in the makespan computation). In order to explore different scenarios, we use values of β ranging from 0.1 to 5.

B. Results

We first present results on the default cluster for all types of workflows, before we study the impact of various parameters, report running times, and summarize the results.

1) *Default cluster*: Fig. 2 (left) shows the relative makespan of DAGHETPART, compared to the makespan found by DAGHETMEM (in percentage), by workflow types, hence the lower the better. For instance, 25% means that the achieved makespan is four times lower than the one of the baseline. When averaging over all types of workflows, the relative makespan is at 41%; hence DAGHETPART is on average $2.44\times$ faster than the baseline.

The trend is that DAGHETPART can achieve the best improvement on larger workflows (big and middle ones). However, even on real-world workflows, the smallest of which has only 11 tasks, DAGHETPART is still $1.59\times$ faster.

Note that DAGHETPART can schedule 13 workflows out of 14 big ones and 31 out of 32 small ones. All middle-sized and all real-world workflows can be scheduled successfully.

It is more challenging for real-world workflows to gain on DAGHETMEM due to several factors. The first reason is their small size: the biggest real-world workflow has 58 tasks, the smallest one only 11. As a consequence, the partitioner is unable to find a partition with the desired number of blocks (36, as the number of nodes in the cluster), so that the workflows are split into 11 to 14 blocks in the first step of

Fig. 2. Relative makespan of DAGHETPART compared to DAGHETMEM on default cluster, in percentage. Smaller is better.

DAGHETPART. This already severely limits the algorithm’s ability to exploit both the parallelism and the heterogeneity. But on top of that, more than half of the tasks in real-world workflows have no historical data. This lead to a situation where relatively few tasks have actual values and a long “tail” of tasks has values of 1. It makes sense to schedule these tiny tasks together on one machine, which also limits the ability to use different machines in the cluster.

2) *Impact of parallelism – small and large clusters:*

Exploiting parallelism is the main reason for the success of DAGHETPART. Being able to utilize even the slower/smaller (memory-wise) processors yields higher improvements on clusters with more nodes. Fig. 2 (right) illustrates this trend. The trend is less obvious for real-world workflows, which is explained by the fact that only one real-world workflow is big enough to benefit from the large cluster. The remaining four do not occupy even all nodes in the default cluster, so that adding new ones has little effect on the makespan.

Moreover, on the large cluster, we are able to schedule all workflows from all types. On the small cluster with 18 nodes, we are able to schedule 13 out of 14 big workflows, 13 out of 17 middle-sized workflows, and 30 out of 32 small workflows. Some workflows cannot be scheduled because there is insufficient memory in the “non-large” clusters.

3) *Impact of heterogeneity – MoreHet and LessHet clusters:*

Fig. 3 (left) illustrates the impact of the heterogeneity level on the relative makespan. Somewhat surprisingly, with more heterogeneity the relative makespans grow, i.e., DAGHETPART wins against the baseline DAGHETMEM by a smaller margin, except for real-world workflows. the absolute makespan values of DAGHETPART become better with more heterogeneity (Fig. 3, right). The reason why the relative values do not improve similarly lies in the way the baseline chooses the processors. It starts with the processor with the largest memory. In the cluster with more heterogeneity, this processor has more memory in relation to the others (compared to the normal scenario). But since the processor has the highest speed, increased even more for this scenario, mapping tasks on it becomes even more advantageous. The strategy of DAGHETMEM to map big parts on these first processors pays off more than in the default cluster, so that it becomes harder for DAGHETPART

Fig. 3. Relative (left, baseline: DAGHETMEM) and absolute (right) makespan of DAGHETPART for different levels of heterogeneity. Smaller is better.

to improve this baseline. Still, regardless of the level of heterogeneity and the type of workflow, DAGHETPART still improves over the baseline in all cases.

As already mentioned, real-world workflows show a different trend from the generated ones. The relative makespan further improves with an increased level of heterogeneity. Here, the small size of the workflows plays a positive role: the workflows are mapped exclusively on the fastest nodes, so when these nodes are stronger, then DAGHETPART, a heuristic that is able to better utilize parallelism, wins. If the size of the workflow requires the use of weaker nodes, then the benefit provided by very fast nodes becomes less pronounced for DAGHETPART.

4) *Impact of CCR:* Fig. 4 shows the effect of different cluster bandwidths on the relative performance of DAGHETPART compared to the baseline. The general trend shows that higher bandwidths allow DAGHETPART to better exploit heterogeneity and produce better makespans. In particular, on small workflows, the relative makespan decreases by 13 percentage points from the smallest bandwidth to the largest one. For the other two groups, the effect is smaller: for big workflows, the difference between the worst and the best relative makespan is only 5.3 points. Real-world workflows prove resistant to changes in bandwidth, because they occupy fewer nodes and the communication costs matter less.

Blocks are based on the partition provided by the DAGP algorithm, which optimizes for edge cut. Even though we merge and repartition the blocks further, this effect of low communication costs seems to persist. This explains the relatively small reaction of DAGHETPART makespan on varying bandwidths.

5) *Running Times:* Table IV and Fig. 5 show the running times of DAGHETPART (running times in the figure are normalized to DAGHETMEM for each workflow). Both algorithms need on real-world workflows less than one second on average. That is why it is of no concern that DAGHETMEM is much faster in this category. Also, the small workflows can be handled in a few seconds by both heuristics, and DAGHETPART is only 63% slower than DAGHETMEM. On middle workflows, both algorithms are nearly equally fast and

Fig. 4. Relative makespan of DAGHETPART compared to DAGHETMEM on default cluster, in percentage, as a function of bandwidth. Smaller is better.

Workflow set	average relative runtime	average absolute runtime (sec)
real-world	406	0.5
small	1.63	2.83
middle	1.02	166.39
big	0.85	647.13

TABLE IV
RELATIVE AND ABSOLUTE RUNNING TIMES OF DAGHETPART

require less than three minutes on average. DAGHETPART is even faster than DAGHETMEM on big workflows; on average, it can map them in less than 11 minutes.

Indeed, the running time of DAGHETMEM is dominated by the effort to compute the optimal memory traversal over the entire workflow. With increasing workflow size, this procedure becomes more and more time-consuming. DAGHETPART computes optimal memory traversals only on the blocks that are smaller in size. Therefore, for bigger workflows, its performance is better than that of DAGHETMEM.

Finally, Fig. 6 also reports the 0.25 and 0.75 quantiles for each workflow type, hence confirming the trend.

6) *Summary*: Overall, DAGHETPART is improving makespans upon the baseline for all workflow sizes and on all cluster configurations, even though the gain is affected by the cluster configuration. In particular, with a large cluster, there is a significant gain, which grows to an improvement of $4\times$ to $5\times$ compared to the baseline (except for real-world workflows that are smaller in size). In terms of heterogeneity, while the relative makespan increases when a more heterogeneous cluster is used (except for real-world workflows), the absolute makespan is still improved. Finally, increasing the communication bandwidth in the cluster has a positive impact on the improvement of the makespan of DAGHETPART, which better exploits the workflow parallelism compared to DAGHETMEM, and hence performs more communications.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have tackled the fundamental but very complex problem of mapping large-scale memory-constrained workflows, modeled as a directed acyclic graph (DAG), onto a heterogeneous platform where each processor may have a different memory capacity and a different processing speed. In this setting, the

Fig. 5. Relative running time of DAGHETPART to DAGHETMEM.

Fig. 6. Absolute running time of DAGHETPART (by workflow types).

objective is to minimize the makespan, *i. e.*, to strive for the best possible performance when executing the workflow. One of the main challenges faced on the path to performance is the fact that workflows are memory-intensive, and some processors may not have the required memory to execute the workflow part assigned to them. While several mapping and scheduling algorithms have been proposed in various models, to the best of our knowledge, the problem of minimizing the makespan while accounting for memory constraints on DAGs has never been addressed.

We proposed both a baseline heuristic, DAGHETMEM, building upon existing work, and a sophisticated novel four-step heuristic, DAGHETPART, which gradually improves a mapping solution that respects all constraints, in order to reduce the makespan. Extensive simulation experiments using both real-world and simulated workflows demonstrate that it is very important to account for the platform heterogeneity and to exploit the parallelism in order to optimize the performance. In particular, on average, the makespan achieved by DAGHETPART is a factor of 2.44 smaller than the one of DAGHETMEM, and it may become up to 5 times smaller for big workflows and large cluster configurations.

The impressive gain showed through simulations that were dictated by realistic workflows and cluster configurations is a good indication that the heuristic should work well in practice, and future work will be devoted to performing real experiments to confirm this trend. We also plan to add one more level of heterogeneity, and consider clusters having communication links with different bandwidths.

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